
Biomarker Analytical Laboratories

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Title: SOP for high-resolution EI+ mass spectral libraries (HR-[EI+]-MS) building via GC-Orbitrap MS

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Summary

High-resolution electron ionization mass spectral libraries are currently limited¹. This SOP describes the construction process of HR-[EI+]-MS libraries from authentic compounds via GC-Orbitrap MS.

The SOP is divided into individual sections:

Section 1. Derivatise metabolite standards

Section 2. Measure via GC Orbitrap

Section 3. Calculate compound properties, derivatives & chemical identifiers

Section 4. Process by MS-DIAL & Section 5. Annotate by MS-FINDER 3.52

Section 6. Merge individual MSPs to a single MSP file by TXTcollector ver. 2.0.2

Section 7. Check the annotated files by MS-LIMA 1.54

Software:

OpenBabel 3.1.1, <https://github.com/openbabel/openbabel/releases>

DataWarrior 5.2.1, <https://openmolecules.org/datawarrior/index.html>

MS-Dial 4.90, <http://prime.psc.riken.jp/compms/msdial/main.html>

MS-Finder 3.52, <http://prime.psc.riken.jp/compms/msfinder/main.html>

TXTcollector 2.0.2, <https://txtcollector.en.softonic.com/?ex=DINS-635.3>

MS-LIMA 1.54, <https://github.com/tipputa/MS-LIMA-Standard>

Section 1: Derivatise metabolite standards

Many compounds require derivatization to be amenable to GC-MS analysis. Here a two-step oximation and trimethylsilylation procedure, commonly performed for metabolites, is described. Application to authentic standards enables the collection of spectra required to generate spectral libraries necessary for automated compound identification and confirmation in samples.

Preparation

Safety information

All work should be conducted in a fume hood.

- MeOx: Danger - corrosive, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard

- Pyridine: Danger - harmful, flammable
- MSTFA: Warning - harmful, flammOpenBabelOpenBabelable

Equipment

- 10 μ L , 100 μ L & 5 mL pipettes
- Dry heat bath with aluminium blocks for 2 mL vials
- Centrifugal evaporator or N₂ evaporator
- Storage boxes for 2 mL vials
- Mini vortex
- Analytical balance (mg accuracy)

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with caps (PTFE septa) and 200 μ L glass inserts
 - Need to make sure caps perfectly fit to prevent evaporation during derivatisation.
- 10 – 20 mL glass tube/ bottle with tight sealing screw cap
 - Caps must be airtight to store pyridine.
- 10 μ L , 100 μ L & 5 mL tips
- Labels for 2 mL vials

Reagents

- GC grade anhydrous pyridine > 99% purity
 - Pyridine will discolour to yellow if old or impure.
- Methoxyamine hydrochloride (MeOx) > 97.5%
 - MeOx reacts with carbonyl groups (e.g. ketones, aldehydes) to form oxime and prevent numerous enol forms that gives rise to many peaks, especially for reducing sugars.
 - Optionally, MeOx reaction can be excluded for compounds without carbonyl group.
- *N*-methyl-*N*-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) > 98%
 - MSTFA replaces free hydroxyl groups with trimethylsilyl (TMS) to reduce polarity and increase volatility (alcohol > phenol > carboxylic acid > amine > amide).
 - Alternatively, we can use MSTFA + 1% trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) as an extra catalyst if many sites are observed to be unreacted. (Typically, it does not make a difference when using pyridine).

MeOx solution (20 mg/mL in pyridine)

- For 5 mL of solution, weigh 100 mg methoxyamine hydrochloride into a glass tube.
- Add 5 mL of pyridine and vortex until dissolved.
 - Solution can be kept for 3 days at room temp. Store double wrapped (e.g. parafilm cap and place glass tube in plastic falcon).

Procedure

Standards

- GC amendable standards requiring derivatisation should be prepared individually.

- Individual compounds form numerous derivative products that need to be related to parent which makes compound mixtures inappropriate for library construction.
- Solvent choice for preparation of stocks is not crucial as extracts are subsequently dried. However, use the highest purity possible.
- To easily attain high-quality spectra on the Q Exactive GC Orbitrap load 1 ng on column (prepare 100 ng/100 μ L in vial). However, anywhere from \sim 5 – 100,000 pg is possible, depending on the compound class.

Standard preparation

1. Label 2 mL glass autosampler vials containing 200 μ L glass inserts.
2. Pipette 100 ng of each GC standard into individual vial with insert.
3. Dry until complete dryness using a centrifugal evaporator or under N_2 .
4. Store dry standards at -80 °C or -20 °C until further processing.

Derivatisation

5. Remove vials from the freezer, decap, and leave for 20 minutes in a fume hood.
 - Moisture prevents derivatization reaction.
6. Pre-heat dry heat block to 50 °C.
7. Add 30 μ L MeOx solution to each standard and incubate at 50 °C for 30 min.
8. Add 70 μ L MSTFA and incubate at 50 °C for 30 min.
9. Remove from heat block & place on ice for a couple of minutes.
10. Inject onto GC-MS system.
 - Derivatives should be injected within 24 hours. At most, derivatives can be injected within 48h if stored free from moisture at -20 °C.

Section 2. Measure via GC Orbitrap

Preparation

Equipment

- 100 μ L pipettes

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with built-in 200 μ L insert and caps (PTFE septa)
- 100 μ L tips

Safety information

- Pyridine: Danger - harmful, flammable
- C_7 - C_{40} alkane series (heptane) – flammable, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard
- Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) series mix (isooctane)– flammable, harmful, health, environmental hazard

Reagents

- C7-C40 Saturated Alkanes Standard; Supelco; cat. 49452-U
- Fully resolved native mono-deca PCB mixture unlabelled; Cambridge Isotope Laboratories; cat. CIL-EC-5434

GC sequence setup

1. Pyridine blank
2. Alkanes**
3. PCBs***
4. Pyridine blank
5. Pyridine blank
6. Procedural blank*
7. Standards 1-10
8. Procedural blank
9. Standards 11-20
10. Procedural blank
11. End with Alkanes, PCBs, and 3 pyridine blanks

NOTE: * procedural blank contains derivatization agents and all sample processing steps including solvents

**** C₇-C₄₀ alkane mix (1 µg/mL in isooctane or pyridine) ~ retention-index lock**

***** PCBs mix (0.1 µg/mL in isooctane or pyridine) ~ system sensitivity check**

Section 3. Calculate compound properties & chemical identifiers

NOTE: The InChI represents the most important chemical identifier to be precisely generated because the others are derived from this one.

NOTE: Use one of the batch conversion links to generate InChI from the chemical name, CAS, or the other available chemical identifier.

- Chemical Translation Service: <https://cts.fiehnlab.ucdavis.edu/batch>
- PubChem: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
- CompTox Chemicals Dashboard: <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/>
- MT Service for MetaCyc: <https://metacyc.org/metabolite-translation-service.shtml>

1. Generate InChI via DataWarrior software:

- a) Open DataWarrior ver. 5.2.1 software
- b) Copy input chemical name
- c) Click Add Structures From Name > Chemistry > From Chemical Structure > Add Standard InChI > File > Save Special >Text file

2. To convert InChI of chemical to SMILES use OpenBabel, follow:

- a) For OpenBabel GUI/---- INPUT FORMAT----, select inchi – InChI format, tick the box Input below (ignore input file) and insert the previously generated InChIs to the yellow-activated space.

- b) Below the CONVERT button select the following boxes:
- Output in canonical form
 - Universal SMILES
 - InChified SMILES
- c) For OpenBabel GUI/---- OUTPUT FORMAT----, select smi – SMILES format, tick the box Output below only (no output file), and click the CONVERT button to generate SMILES.
- 3. To convert SMILES of chemical to SMILES w/o salt entering the library annotation, follow:**
- a) For OpenBabel GUI/---- INPUT FORMAT----, select smi – SMILES format, tick the box Input below (ignore input file) and insert the previously generated SMILES to the yellow-activated space.
- b) Below the CONVERT button select the following boxes:
- c) Remove all but the largest contiguous fragment
- d) Do not include isotopic or chiral markings
- e) For OpenBabel GUI/---- OUTPUT FORMAT----, select smi – SMILES format, tick the box Output below only (no output file) and click the CONVERT button to generate SMILES w/o salt.
- 4. Transform SMILES to InChIKey and calculate molecular formula and monoisotopic mass**
- a) Open DataWarrior ver. 5.2.1 software > Copy input SMILES > Chemistry > From Chemical Structure > Add InChI-Key > OK
- b) Open DataWarrior ver. 5.2.1 software > Copy input SMILES > Chemistry > From chemical structure > Add Molecular Formula
- c) Chemistry > From chemical structure > Calculate Properties > ✓ Monoisotopic mass > OK
- 5. Predict derivatized structures**

NOTE: Methoxyamine hydrochloride (MeOX) and N-Methyl – N –(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) are commonly used for derivatization of small molecules to decrease boiling points and increase stability of GC-MS analysis. Depending on the temperature and time, the efficiency of derivatization changes; for library building is needed to predict all possible derivatization prediction options:

- **optimal derivatization** $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-HN-TMS$
- **over – derivatization** $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-N(TMS)_2$
- **incomplete derivatization** $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-NH_2$

The MetaboloDerivatizer software converts SMILES of native compound to derivatized form as SMILES. (see [MetaboloDerivatizer tutorial.pdf \(riken.jp\)](#))

- a) Open MetaboloDerivatizer software and copy input (SMILES of native compound) > For batch SMILES conversion prepare SMILES list.txt (Do not use any header and prepare one SMILES in row)
Click > Browse > Load SMILES list.txt
- b) Choose: $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-HN-TMS$ (optimal) (then $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-N(TMS)_2$ and $R-NH_2 \rightarrow R-NH_2$)
- c) Convert and the results will be generated in the same directory
- 6. After derivative structure prediction via MetaboloDerivatizer software convert smiles to canonical form**
- a) For OpenBabel GUI/---- INPUT FORMAT----, select smi-SMILES format format, tick the box Input below (ignore input file) and insert the previously generated InChIs to the yellow-activated space.

- b) Below the CONVERT button select the following boxes:
- Output in canonical form
 - Universal SMILES
 - InChified SMILES
- c) For OpenBabel GUI/---- OUTPUT FORMAT----, select smi – SMILES format, tick the box Output below only (no output file) and click the CONVERT button to generate SMILES.
7. Transform SMILES to InChIKey format and calculate molecular formula and monoisotopic mass via DataWarrior ver. 5.2.1 software (see previous processing)

Section 4. Process by MS-DIAL 4.90

1. Open MS-DIAL ver. 4.70 software > Click File > New project > Project file path: Browse: the combined folder

NOTE: Project path file should contain files of authentic compounds in mzML format

2. Enter parameters within the bookmark:
- **Ionization type:** Hard ionization (GC/MS)
 - **Separation type:** Chromatography (GC, LC, CE, or SFC)
 - **MS method type:** Conventional LC/MS or data-dependent MS/MS
 - **Data type (MS1):** Profile data
 - **Ion mode:** Positive ion mode
- Advanced:**
- Instrument type: GC-EI-Orbitrap
 - Instrument: Q Exactive GC Orbitrap GC-MS/MS
 - Authors: Biomarker Analytical_Lab, RECETOX, Masaryk University (CZ)
 - License: CC BY-NC
 - Collision energy: 70
3. Click Next
4. Click Browse > Select raw files > Open > Set sample type (Sample, Standard, QC, Blank) and Class ID

NOTE: Set Sample as Class ID 1, QC as Class ID 2 (or different), Procedural blank as Class ID 3 (or a different number)

NOTE: Use your Procedural blank (containing derivatization agent) as a Blank filter, do not upload your instrumental blank (= solvent blank) containing only solvent without derivatization agent to prevent averaging blank and false noise (blank) reduction

3. Click Next
4. Fill in the parameters settings: for each bookmark with advanced settings place the selected parameters shown in Table 4.
5. Identification > Index file > Click Set > Load Alkanes.txt for the current batch > Right click > Auto fill > Set

C7-C40 alkane series are used for external non-isothermal Kováts retention-indexing (from temperature programming, using the definition of Van den Dool and Kratz)³

5. Click ✓ Together with Alignment > Finish and wait for data processing

NOTE: To check parameters entered: MS-DIAL/Data Processing/All processing (from peak detection).

Data viewing using MS-DIAL 4.90

Figure 1. MS-DIAL 4.90 – Peak spot viewer

NOTE: In Peak spot viewer, each spot denotes the detected peak of each mass (m/z) trace: blue spots describe peaks of lower abundance in the sample, red spots describe peaks of higher abundance, and green spots describe peaks of middle abundance. The reverse triangle is an important description of the recognized detected metabolites. One click on the reverse triangles to see detail of the detected (deconvoluted) peak.

Figure 2. MS-DIAL 4.90 – Alignment spot viewer

NOTE: MS – DIAL ver. 4.90 can automatically identify the metabolite peaks by the similarity calculation of retention index and EI spectrum with the reference databases > alignment result file registered in Alignment navigator > Alignment spot viewer shows

6. Survey scan (MS1) spectrum > MS1 peak of the focused peak
7. EIC of focused spot > extracted ion chromatogram of the quant mass of the focused peak
8. Exp. vs. Ref. displays the EI spectrum (blue or black) and the reference MS/MS spectrum (red)
9. Click ✓ Blank filter
10. Double click AliqnmentResult
11. File navigator > Double-click on your file

Figure 3. MS-DIAL 4.90

12. Hold the right button and drag > zoom in and out (only vertical zoom) see Figure 3.
13. One click on the reverse triangles and the detected (deconvoluted) peak appears in the right window see Figure 3.
14. Compare EI spectra and retention index (RI) with available reference mass spectra database:
 - <http://gmd.mpimp-golm.mpg.de/>
 - <https://webbook.nist.gov/chemistry/>
15. Right click on the reverse triangle > Search formula and structure > go to **MS-FINDER program** > Deconvoluted

Section 5. Annotate by MS-Finder 3.52

1. MS-FINDER software will automatically open (see Section 4)

NOTE: MS-FINDER is a universal program for compound annotation for EI-MS (GC/MS) and MS/MS data, see: <https://mtbinfo-team.github.io/mtbinfo.github.io/MS-FINDER/tutorial.html>

2. Use MS-FINDER SETTINGS see Table 5.
3. The *File navigator* section includes the analyte file named by the creation date & time, name, scan number, RI
4. By clicking the analyte file, the *File information* boxes are filled in automatically, then check and modify:
 - Name: Unknown, rewrite by the analyte name
 - Scan number, Retention time (min) & CCS (\AA^2): filled in automatically

- Precursor m/z: as a Precursor m/z use the highest mass in spectrum which is less than equal to the monoisotopic mass
 - Precursor type: [M]⁺
 - Ion mode: Positive filled in automatically
 - Spectrum Type: Centroid
 - Collision energy: 70
 - Formula: write formula (with TMS groups)
 - Ontology: -
 - SMILES: write SMILES (for derivative structure)
 - InChIKey: write InChIKey
 - Comment: -
1. Analysis/Fragment Annotation (single) → Peak assignment setting, check, and Finish.
 2. Analysis/Fragment Annotation (batch job), use following the annotation of 10 analytes generated by “MS-DIAL 4.70/File/Open project” & “MS-FINDER 3.52” steps.

NOTE: For each annotated analyte, it saves a appropriate folder including SDF file (.sdf), FDT file (.fgt), and MAT shortcut to the MSDIAL_TEMP folder.

3. Click Export > Export peak annotation results in MSP format → Save every ten annotated analytes to a single MSP file, i.e.: MSP1 for analytes 1-10, MSP2 for analytes 11-20, etc.

NOTE: First, ideally create Batch 1.msp file of approximately 10 compounds and then merge multiple Batch.msp files into a single file using TXTcollector ver. 2.0.2 software.

Section 6. Merge individual MSPs to a single MSP file by TXTcollector

4. Open TXTcollector software
5. Click Extension and Separation
6. Double click extensions > add msp > File > Save
7. Choose .msp format
8. Click Browse Folders and choose multiple individual .msp files to be merge to one .msp file
9. Click Combine all files and save as new single msp. file

Section 7. Check the annotated files by MS-LIMA 1.54

1. Open MS-LIMA 1.54
2. File/Import/Import (without auto saving), select and open the MSP file to be inspected
3. Setting/Setting Window → Parameter setting/Key of compound grouping → InChI, save and reopen the MSP file according to the point 1.

NOTE: Do not use autosaving because MS-LIMA ver. 1.54 could rewrite library.msp

NOTE: Check your isomers, fragment annotation, etc.

Table 1: GC-MS method setup - autosampler settings

TriPlus RSH		Comments
General		
Injection port		
Injector	Injector A (SSL)	
Type	Single	
Injection mode		
Mode	Basic	
Rapid mode		
Rapid mode	Disable	
Syringe type		
Syringe volume (µL)	10	
Needle length (mm)	57	
Sampling		
Sample volume (µL)	2	*Set in method sequence*
Plunger strokes	0	
Air and filling mode	Custom	
Air volume (µL)	0	
Filling volume (µL)	0	
Sampling depth in vials		
Sample vial depth (mm)	\	
Bottom sense	Yes	
Height from bottom (mm)	1.5	
Injection		
Injection depth	Custom	
Pre-injection dwell time (s)	0	
Post-injection dwell time (s)	0.1	
Fast injection	Off	
Injection depth (mm)	45	
Penetration speed (mm/s)	90	
Sample viscosity		
Sample type	Custom	
Sample pullup speed (µL/s)	0.4	
Delay after plunger strokes (s)	1.5	
Viscosity delay (s)	2	
Washes		
Washes		
Number of solvents(s)	Multiple	
Wash station	Standard wash station	

Solvent A	nonane
Solvent B	toluene
Solvent C	acetone
Solvent D	nonane
E position	waste

Pre-injection

Solvent	A \ \ \
Cycles	4
Solvent volume (μL)	7.0

Rinse

Rinses	0
Rinse Volume (UI)	1

Post-injection

Solvent	\ B C D
Cycles	7
Solvent volume (μL)	7.0

Sync**GC synchro start**

Synchro type	Standard
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Advanced**Advanced parameters**

Wash solvent depth (mm)	45
Waste depth (mm)	10
Needle speed in vial (mm/s)	10
Solvent filling speed ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	1
Bubble elimin. pullup ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	5
Delay between strokes (s)	2.0

Consumable:

- Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; (0.25-0.53 mm) for GC guard column 0.53 ID; Restek; cat. 23896
- Ferrule, SilTite; Replacements for MicroUnion; (0.25-0.25 mm); Restek; cat. 23894
- Connector, SilTite MicroUnion; Restek; cat. 23885
- Column: Rxi-5Sil MS; 0.25 μm , 0.25 mmID; 15m length; Restek; cat. 13620 (use 15 m column)
- Post-column: Rxi Guard Column 0.25 mmID; 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10029 (install only 2 m)
- Pre-column: Rxi Guard Column; 0.53 mmID, 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10054 (install only 2 m)
- Collared Column Nut, Self Tightening MSD; Agilent Technologies; cat. G3440-8113
- To MS: Ferules VG1 0.4 mm; 85% Vespel/15% Graphite (Fits column ID \leq 0.25 mm); Restek; cat. 27071

- To inlet: VG1, 85% Vespel/15% Graphite Compact, 1/16, 0.8mm ID, 50-pk; Restek; cat.27075
- Septa type: Thermolite Plus, 11 mm; Restek; cat. 23864
- Liner type: Topaz Liner, Splitless, Gooseneck. w/wool; Restek; cat. 23303

Table 2: GC-MS method setup – GC settings

TRACE 1300 Series GC				Comments
Oven				*Trace 1310*
Ramps				
		Rate (C/min)	Temp (C)	Hold time (min)
Initial			80	0.5
	1	40	200	0.5
	2	40	260	0.5
	3	55	330	4.0
Options				
Max temp.		340 °C		
Prep-run timeout		10 min		
Equilibration time		0.5 min		
Ready delay		0.00 min		
Oven on		Yes		
S/SL (front)				
S/SL mode		Splitless w/Surge		
Inlet				
Temp	On		290°C	
Split flow	On		50.0 mL/min	
Split ratio		\		
Splitless time		0.80 min		
Surge				
Surge pressure		140.00 kPA		
Surge duration		0.80 min		
Septum purge				
Purge flow		3.0 mL/min		
Constant septum purge		Yes		
Stop purge for		\		
Carrier mode		Constant flow		
Carrier flow				
Flow	On		1.2 mL/min	
Carrier options				
Vacuum compensation		On		

Carrier gas saver	On
Gas saver flow	15.0 mL/min
Gas saver time	3.00 min

Aux. Temperatures**Auxilliary temperature control**

Transfer Line 1	On	280C
Transfer Line 2	On	280C

Table 3: GC-MS method setup – MS settings**Q Exactive GC-Orbitrap MS****Comments****Global Settings**

User role	Advanced
Use lock masses	off
Lock mass injection	\

Time

Method duration	11.50 min
Customized Tolerances (+/-)	
Lock Masses	\
Inclusion	\
Exclusion	\
Mass Tags	\
Dynamic Exclusion	\

EI/CI Source

Filament on delay	2.00 min
MS transfer line temp	250 °C
Ion source temp	280 °C
Ionization mode	EI
CI gas type	None
CI gas flow	0.00 mL/min
Use tune emission current	TRUE
Emission current	50.0 µA
Use tune electron energy	FALSE
Electron energy	70 eV
Use tune file C-Trap energy offset	TRUE
C-Trap energy offset	0.0 V
Cal gas level	Off

Properties of Full MS-SIM

Experiment	Full MS — SIM
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General

Runtime	2 to 11.5 min
Polarity	Positive

Full MS

Microscans	1	
Resolution	60,000	
AGC target	1.00E+06	
Maximum IT	auto	
Scan range	70 to 700 m/z	
Spectrum data type	Profile	
Setup		
Tunefiles		
General		
Switch Count 0		
Tune scan range	70-700	Update each acquisition - Tune to TIC
Res	60,000	
AGC	1.00E+06	
Max inject	auto	
MS transfer	250	
Ion source	280	

Table 4: Parameter setting used to process acquired RAW files by MS-DIAL 4.90

Start up a project		
Ionization type	Hard ionization (GC/MS)	
Separation type	Chromatography (GC, LC, CE, or SCF)	
MS method type	Conventional LC/MS or data dependent MS/MS	
Data type (MS1)	Profile	
Data type (MS/MS)	Profile data	
Ion mode	Positive ion mode	
Target omics	Metabolomics	
Advanced: add further metadata	Instrument Type: GC-EI-Orbitrap Instrument: Q Exploris GC Orbitrap GC-MS/MS Authors: Biomarker Analytical_Lab, RECETOX, Masaryk University (CZ) License: CC BY-NC Collision energy: 70	
Data collection		
Mass range begin	70 Da	
Mass range end	700 Da	
Advanced	Retention time begin	0 min
	Retention time end	100 min
Multithreading	Number of threads	15

Peak detection		
Minimum peak height	50 000	
Accurate MS	True	
Mass slice width	0.05	
Mass accuracy for centroiding	0.05	
Advanced	Smoothing level	3
Maximum charged number	Average peak width	10
MS1Dec		
Signa window value	0.3	
El spectra cut off	1	
Identification		
RI or RT	Use retention index (RI)	
Index file	Load C7-C40 alkane series file (see NOTE below)	
Index type	Alkanes	
MSP file	Load C7-C40 alkane series file (see NOTE below)	
Retention index tolerance	20	
Retention time tolerance	100	
m/z tolerance	0.5	
El similarity cut off	60	
Identification score cut off	70	
Use retention information for scoring	True	
Use retention information for filtering	False	
Use quant masses defined in MSP format file	False	10
Only report the top hit		
Alignment		
Result name		
Reference file		
RI or RT	RI	
Retention index tolerance	5	
Retention time tolerance	0.075	
El similarity tolerance	70	
Advanced		
Retention time factor	0.7	
El similarity factor	0.3	
Identification after alignment	True	
Gap filling by compulsion	True	
Choose base peak's m/z for rep. quant mass	False	
Filtering		
Peak count filter	0	
N% detected in at least one group	0	

Remove features based on blank information	True
Sample mas/blank average	5
Keep 'reference matched' metabolite features	True
Keep removable features and assign the tag	True

Table 5: Parameter setting used to annotate processed RAW files by MS-Finder 3.52

Method	
Search option	
Spectral database search	True
Formula prediction and structure elucidation by in silico fragmenter	True
Spectral database option	
Use internal experimental library (MassBank, GNPS, ReSpect)	True
Basic	
Mass tolerance setting	
Mass tolerance type	ppm
Mass tolerance (MS1), (\pm ppm)	5
Mass tolerance (MS2), (\pm ppm)	5
Abundance setting	
Relative abundance cut-off (%)	1
Mass range setting	
Mass range max (Da)	2 000
Mass range min (Da)	0
Formula finder	
Formula calculation setting	
LEWIS and SENIOR check	True
Isotopic ratio tolerance (%)	20
Element ratio check (covering)	Extended range (99.99%)
Element probability check	True
Element selection	True: O, N, P, S, F, Cl, Br, I, Si
TMS-MEOX derivative compound	True
Minimum TMS count	1
Minimum MEOX count	0
Options	
Maximum report number (up to 100)	100
Time out (-1 means infinite), (min)	-1
Advanced settings for AIF	False
Structure finder	
Tree depth	3
Maximum report number	100
Time out (-1 means infinite)	-1
Cut off for structure elucidation (0-10, total score)	0
Cut off for spectral match (0-100, %)	80

Data source	Settings are not important
Retention time	Settings are not important
CCS	
Use experimental CCS values for searching	True
CCS tolerance (Ao ²)	10
Use CCS to exclude candidates	True

Table 6: Parameter setting for MS-LIMA 1.54 by MS-LIMA 1.54 used to check the annotated files

Basic settings	
MS 2 tolerance (Da)	0.0035
RT tolerance for difference checking (min)	5
Min. number for consensus (samples)	1
Key of compound grouping	InChI
Visualization settings	
Number of decimal places of m/z value	5
Each spectrum height in multiple viewer (pixel)	200
Additional settings	
Interval time to auto export (milliseconds)	1000

Literature:

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